

Impact of Mergers and Acquisitions on the Financial Performance of Selected Indian Healthcare and Pharmaceuticals Companies

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Abstract

The mergers and acquisitions (M&A) strategy is an essential component of business strategy and a significant alternative for achieving strategic growth. The present study aims to examine the impact of mergers on the financial performance of selected Indian healthcare and pharmaceutical companies from 2018 to 2021. The research relies on secondary data from 13 merging companies to analyze key financial ratios, such as liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency, by using descriptive statistics and a paired sample t-test. The findings reveal that there is no statistically significant difference in the financial performance of the companies before and after the mergers. The study is limited by its small sample size, short time horizon, and sector-specific focus. Future researchers may address these limitations by expanding the sample size, measuring long-term impact, and selecting cross-sectional sectors to measure the impact of M&A on firms' performance.

Keywords

Mergers, Acquisitions, Healthcare, Pharmaceutical Sector, Financial Performance

Introduction

The world is evolving rapidly due to the effects of globalization and rapid technological advancements (Kumar & Bansal, 2008). The presence of a free market leads to increased economic development, which in turn impacts the level of competition in both domestic and international markets (Irayanti, 2019). M&A is a crucial component of corporate strategy and a significant option for strategic growth (Rani et al., 2015). Globalization, liberalization,

technological advancements, and a competitive business climate have increased the importance of mergers and acquisitions globally (Leepsa & Mishra, 2012; Usman et al., 2010). These strategies will help businesses to adopt new technologies, a post-globalization economy, and shift towards profit pools (Baird et al., 2025). The performance of M&A deals has been the subject of ongoing discussion (Rani et al., 2015). M&A performance can be assessed from three key perspectives: the financial approach, which looks at profits, stock prices, and revenue growth; the strategic approach, which evaluates whether the merger or acquisition supports long-term business goals; and the organizational approach, which focuses on integration success, management efficiency, and cultural fit (Vinocur et al., 2023). Plenty of studies have demonstrated the beneficial consequences of mergers and acquisitions. Business pursues mergers and acquisitions for a variety of reasons such as to increase market share, access innovative resources to lower the risks involved in developing a new good or service, tax benefits (Austin & Dunham, 2022), maximize efficiency through economies of scale and scope, alter the competitive landscape, improve financial performance, synergy, diversification (geographic or business), cross-selling, resource transfer, vertical integration, managerial hubris, and combining related enterprises under one management (Hit et al., 2007; King et al., 2008), increasing profitability, strengthen balance sheet (Katz, 2021), achieving organizational synergy in workplace, reducing startup cost, enhance shareholder wealth, asset returns and equity returns (Sharma & Singh, 2023; Vinila, 2023), addressing inefficiencies from prior expansions, combining fragmented players for efficiency, and expanding up to compete worldwide by focusing on core capabilities. These strategies allow businesses to align with market demands and emphasize the creation of value (Chauhan, 2011). Despite the reasons for successful M&A, some studies revealed unsuccessful M&A (Aggarwal & Garg, 2022) due to such reasons as high acquisition cost, unrealized forecasts, incorrect target selection, and cultural differences.

M&A in the healthcare and pharmaceutical industries is notoriously difficult due to their highly regulated structure. Due diligence is necessary for successful transactions, encompassing legal compliance, data protection compliance, contractual obligations with key medical professionals, land and asset title verification, and regulatory approvals from authorities such as the Competition Commission of India. The healthcare industry is vital to the development of a nation like India, which has a large population and a thriving economy. The surge in deal activity in the healthcare and pharmaceutical industries is driving significant changes in their infrastructure, which is more than merely a sign of

economic prosperity (Shah et al., 2024). This is primarily due to increased demand, affordability, and structural reforms..

At the global level, the value of M&A activity increased by 15%, reaching approximately USD 3.5 trillion, while deal volume increased by almost 7% (Baird et al., 2025). With 2,186 deals valued at USD 116 billion, 2024 was a remarkable year for Indian deal-making.

Leading healthcare companies can enter Tier 2 and Tier 3 cities because of increased M&A activity, which brings advanced facilities and expertise. Additionally, they are creating new job opportunities, which are helping these areas' socioeconomic development. The continuous surge of mergers and acquisitions in India's healthcare industry is essentially creating a more comprehensive and equitable healthcare environment, with long-reaching

advantages that go far beyond monetary gains (Shah et al., 2024). The COVID-19 pandemic significantly transformed the healthcare and pharmaceutical sectors, underscoring the necessity for enhanced supply chains, research and development, and hospital capacity. To remain relevant, businesses adopted new models in 2020, which has been viewed as the pandemic year, while 2021 is regarded as the golden age of Indian transactions. Additionally, it saw domestic companies grow stronger and increase their presence both domestically and internationally.

However, M&A is an ongoing subject of discussion due to its mixed results. There is still no consensus on whether M&A improves a firm's performance or not. The present study seeks to examine the impact of mergers on the financial performance of selected Indian healthcare and pharmaceutical companies. Using a paired sample t-test, key financial ratios such as liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and turnover ratio are examined during the three-year pre- and post-merger periods.

Objective of study

The objectives of the present studies are as follows

1. To examine the impact of mergers on the financial performance of selected Indian healthcare and pharmaceutical companies.
2. To analyze key financial ratios—such as liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency during the pre- and post merger periods.
3. To determine whether the observed changes in financial performance are statistically significant using paired sample t-tests

Review of Literature

Positive impact of M&A on performance

There are numerous studies available in the literature that indicate the positive impact of M&A on firm performance. Chakraborty and Kattuman (2023) analyze the impact of M&A in the Indian pharmaceutical industry during the period of 2000-2015. Their results show that the firm performance of merging firms improved after the merger. Dhir et al. (2020) analyze the post-acquisition performance from the standpoint of Bharti Airtel's acquisition of Zain in South Africa. They find that earnings per share and return on equity increase after the post-acquisition. Li and Geng (2024) conduct the empirical study are conducted using data of Chinese listed companies in the energy sector from 2010 to 2020 as samples to examine the effects of M&A activity in the sector on corporate environmental investment by using data from Chinese listed companies in the energy sector from 2010 to 2020 were used as sample. They find that M&A in the energy sector has a positive impact on improving the EPI. In the context of Indian M&A deals, Kalsie & Singh (2023) reveal an interesting dynamic between deal size and synergy gains. Their results show that there is a trade-off between financial and operational synergies in Indian M&A deals. Larger transactions may have greater difficulties in attaining operational synergy, even while they are more likely to produce financial gains. On the other hand, smaller businesses may be better at achieving the overall advantages of M&A, perhaps as a result of their less complicated structure and integration procedure. Aggarwal & Garg (2022) measure the performance of the manufacturing & service sector based on long-term and short-term. In service sector companies achieve synergies are achieved faster due to a similar integration process, but in the case of the manufacturing sector, firms show significant improvement only in the long term. Kumar and Bansal (2008) examined the impact of M&A on corporate performance in India and revealed that many acquiring firms were able to achieve synergy in the long run. Rani et al (2015) find that M&A between 2003-2008 resulted in considerable improvement in the profitability & operational performance of the acquiring firms. The data indicate that these firms effectively increased their operating profit margins, reduced expenses, and improved liquidity mostly through enhanced operational efficiency rather than increased asset utilization.

Negative impact of M&A on performance

Jain et al. (2023) examine the post-acquisition performance of emerging market companies from 2001 to 2017. They find that after the acquisition, Indian companies' performance drastically declined. There has been a noticeable decline in their profitability, assets, as well as cost efficiency. However, the profitability of Chinese companies has remained the same after CBAs. Satapathy & Kaushik (2021) determine whether M&A deals improve the acquiring companies' performance by creating synergy, using both cash flow and financial ratio measures. Using a matching firm technique and comparing the cash flow of the acquiring firms to industry trends, the study reveals that rather than benefitting from the expected synergies, these firms experience a decline in

performance. Overall, the results indicate that, after the M&A, the performance of acquiring companies deteriorates. Reddy et al (2019) analyze the impact of M&A on the value of acquiring companies in India and China by using three different methods to measure returns. The analysis concludes that, while one method (mean-adjusted return) showed that Chinese companies create value after M&A, the other two methods (market-adjusted return & OLS adjusted return) did not. They suggest that M&A did not improve shareholder value in China. On the other hand, in India, all three methods show no improvement in companies' value after M&A. According to Kumar (2009) mergers do not always result in increased financial performance for the acquiring companies. Post-merger asset turnover, profitability & solvency show no significant increase over the pre-merger level. Jain et al. (2020) find that both frequent & first-time Indian acquirers face declining performance after cross-border acquisition, likely driven by managerial overconfidence & poor strategic judgments rather than synergy development. Patel (2018) studies Indian banks from 2003-04 to 2013-14 and reveals that mergers negatively impacted return on assets, return on equity, net profit ratio, yields on advances & investment. However, earnings per share, business per employee, and profit per employee improved post-merger due to better human resource utilization. While assets, equity, investments & advances increased, their yields decreased due to underutilization.

Mixed Impact of M&A on firm performance

Larasati et al. (2017) studied the pre- and post-M&A financial performance of 24 companies from 2010 to 2014 using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Their results indicate that only debt to equity ratio increases after M&A, but the current ratio, net profit margin, price-earnings ratio, and total asset turnover decrease after M&A. Leepsa & Mishra (2012) find mixed results relating to the post-merger financial performance of companies. They find that liquidity and profitability are improved after the merger, but not statistically significantly. Akhtar & Nosheen (2022) M&A between banks & fintech start-ups boosts operational performance, liquidity & financial leverage, but long-

term market performance suffers due to concerns about integration & sustainability. Mishra et al. (2010) examined how mergers and acquisitions have influenced the financial performance of Indian pharmaceutical companies and determined the impact of M&A on their profitability. Their finding shows that the company's profitability is positively connected to its size, export, and import intensities & sales efforts, but adversely related to market share and product demand. In conclusion, they found that M&A activities have no substantial impact on profitability. Chauhan (2011) examined the impact of mergers on the shareholder value of 56 selected firms by using regression analysis during the period of 1 April 1999 to 31 March 2000 and found that Operating expenses, profit margins, ROCE, and expense ratios all have a substantial impact on shareholder value creation. However, inter-company and inter industry assessments demonstrate that mergers do not increase shareholder value creation.

Methodology

The study focuses on 13 pharmaceutical and healthcare firms in India that merged between 2018 and 2021. The companies were selected based on the following criteria-

1. Only BSE/NSE-listed companies were selected.
2. Financial information is available for three years before and after the merger.
3. Mergers completed within the specified period.
4. Cross-border mergers were excluded.

Descriptive statistics and a paired sample t-test were used to analyse the financial performance.

Result and Discussion

Table 1. Profitability analysis of selected companies

Profitability ratio	Mean (Pre)	Mean (Post)	t-Value	p-Value
Operating Profit Margin (OPM)	19.41	20.23	0.44	0.667
Net Profit Margin (NPM)	5.42	7.87	0.83	0.420
Return on Capital Employed (ROCE)	7.96	9.30	0.66	0.524
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	12.21	11.86	-0.11	0.915

To examine the financial performance of the selected pharmaceutical and healthcare firms, we used four important profitability ratios.

In the case of OPM, the null hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is 0.667, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. However, the mean of OPM is slightly increased from 19.41 to 20.23. Despite of small improvement, there is no statistically significant change in OPM.

After analysis, it is found that the mean of NPM is increased from 5.42 to 7.87, but the null hypothesis is rejected because the p-value is 0.420, which exceeds the significance

level. So the null hypothesis is accepted, and there is no statistically significant change in NPM.

After the merger, the mean of ROCE increased from 7.96 to 9.30. Yet the p-value is 0.524, which is greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted, and there is no significant difference between before and after the merger.

Analysing the RONW, the null hypothesis is accepted because there is no statistically significant difference between before and after the merger, as the p-value is 0.915, which is greater than 0.05. The mean of ROCE is also decreased from 12.21 to 11.86, which shows the negative impact of merger activity on RONW.

Table 2. Liquidity analysis of selected firms

Liquidity ratio	Mean (Pre)	Mean (Post)	t-Value	p-Value
Current Ratio (CR)	1.72	1.72	0.01	0.989
Quick Ratio (QR)	1.32	1.21	-0.45	0.662

The mean of the current ratio remains the same before and after the merger, indicating that there is no statistically significant change in the current ratio. We accept the null hypothesis because the p-value is 0.989, which is greater than 0.05.

After the merger, the mean of the quick ratio decreased from 1.32 to 1.21. We reject the null hypothesis because there is a significant difference between before and after the merger—P-value 0.662, which is also less than 0.05.

Table 3. Solvency analysis of selected firms

Solvency ratio	Mean (Pre)	Mean (Post)	t-Value	p-Value
Debt-to-Equity Ratio (D/E)	0.514	0.489	-0.28	0.786
Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR)	55.05	24.27	-1.22	0.246

The mean of Debt to equity ratio has declined from 0.514 to 0.489, which shows that there is no significant change in debt to equity ratio after the merger. The null hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is 0.786, which exceeds the 0.05 significance level.

After the merger, there is also decreased the mean value of the Interest coverage ratio decreased from 55.05 to 24.27. p-value is 0.246, which is still above 0.05, so the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4. Efficiency analysis of selected firms |

Efficiency ratio	Mean (Pre)	Mean (Post)	t-Value	p-Value
Asset Turnover Ratio (ATR)	0.76	0.73	-0.54	0.598
Debtor Turnover Ratio (DTR)	5.59	6.22	1.71	0.113

After the merger, the Asset turnover ratio decreased slightly from 0.76 to 0.73, indicating no statistically significant change. The null hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is 0.598, also greater than 0.05. M&A activity has not had a substantial impact on how effectively businesses use their assets to generate revenue.

The mean of the debtor turnover ratio has increased from 5.59 to 6.22. Despite this, the null hypothesis is accepted because the p-value is 0.113, which is greater than 0.05

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper is to examine the impact of mergers on the financial performance of healthcare and pharmaceutical companies, three years before and after the merger. To measure the financial performance, the study used profitability, liquidity, solvency, and efficiency ratios. 13 healthcare and pharma companies were examined by using a paired sample t-test. The analysis shows that there is no statistically significant difference in profitability, liquidity, solvency, and efficiency ratios before and after the merger. In a short period, the firms cannot improve their financial performance. Another reason behind this was the period of COVID-19. Some indicators, such as Quick Ratio, Interest Coverage Ratio, and Return on Net Worth, had minor reductions; while others, like the Net Profit Margin and Return on Capital Employed, showed just slight improvements. The results are not statistically significant because in the case of all the financial indicators, the p-value is greater than the 5 percent significance level. The present study has certain limitations. Firstly, the findings of the study may not generalize due to the small sample size of the short-term three-year pre and post-measurement, which may not capture the long-term results. Third, the study only focuses on healthcare and pharmaceutical companies. Additionally, during the study period, the financial ratio may have been affected by external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic and changes in accounting standards (for example, the shift from IGAAP to IND-AS). Future researchers may address these limitations by expanding the sample size, measuring

long-term impact, and selecting cross sectional sectors to measure the impact of M&A on firms' performance.

References

1. Aggarwal, Pooja, and Sandeep Garg. "Impact of Mergers and Acquisitions on Accounting-Based Performance of Acquiring Firms in India." *Global Business Review*, vol. 23, no. 1, 2022, pp. 218–236.
2. Akhtar, Q., and S. Nosheen. "The Impact of Fintech and Banks M&A on Acquirer's Performance: A Strategic Win or Loss?" *Borsa Istanbul Review*, vol. 22, no. 6, 2022, pp. 1195–1208.
3. Austin, Rebekah E., and Lee M. Dunham. "Do FinTech Acquisitions Improve the Operating Performance or Risk Profiles of Acquiring Firms?" *Journal of Economics and Business*, vol. 121, 2022, 106078.
4. Baird, L., D. Harding, D. Stafford, K. Grass, S. Kumar, R. Telzak, Bain & Company, CEPRES GmbH, Bain Capability Network, Bain Capability Network Labs, and DealEdge. *Global M&A Report 2025*. 2025.
5. Chakraborty, I., and P. Kattuman. "The Impact of Mergers and Acquisitions on Performance of Firms: A Pre- and Post-TRIPS Analysis of India's Pharmaceutical Industry." *Asia and the Global Economy*, vol. 3, no. 2, 2023, pp. 1–17.
6. Chauhan, P. "Effect of Mergers on Financial Performance: A Study of Indian Corporate." *Indian Journal of Accounting*, vol. 41, no. 2, 2011, pp. 18–26.
7. Dhir, S., V. Ongsakul, Z. U. Ahmed, and R. Rajan. "Integration of Knowledge and Enhancing Competitiveness: A Case of Acquisition of Zain by Bharti Airtel." *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 119, 2020, pp. 674–684.
8. Hitt, Michael A., R. Duane Ireland, and Robert E. Hoskisson. *Strategic Management: Competitiveness and Globalisation Concepts*. South-Western, 2007.
9. Irayanti, L. "How Merger and Acquisition Affect Firm Performance and Its Quality." *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 2019, pp. 42–53.
10. Jain, S., S. Kashiramka, and P. K. Jain. "Do Frequent Acquirers Outperform in Cross-Border Acquisitions? A Study of Indian Companies." *Review of International Business and Strategy*, vol. 30, no. 4, 2020, pp. 491–514.
11. Jain, S., S. Kashiramka, and P. K. Jain. "Performance of Cross-Border Acquirers from India and China: Its Sustainability in the Long Run?" *Review of International Business and Strategy*, vol. 34, no. 1, 2023, pp. 40–61.
12. Kalsie, A., and N. Singh. "Deal Size and Synergy Gains: A Case of Indian M&A." *Vikalpa*, vol. 48, no. 4, 2023, pp. 255–268.
13. Katz, Michael L. "Big Tech Mergers: Innovation, Competition for the Market, and the Acquisition of Emerging Competitors." *Information Economics and Policy*, vol. 54, 2021, pp. 1–37.
14. King, David R., Rebecca J. Slotegraaf, and Ida Kesner. "Performance Implications of Firm Resource Interactions in the Acquisition of R&D-Intensive Firms." *Organization Science*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2008, pp. 327–340.
15. Kumar, R. "Post-Merger Corporate Performance: An Indian Perspective." *Management Research News*, vol. 32, no. 2, 2009, pp. 145–157.
16. Kumar, S., and L. K. Bansal. "The Impact of Mergers and Acquisitions on Corporate Performance in India." *Management Decision*, vol. 46, no. 10, 2008, pp. 1531–1543.
17. Larasati, N. D., Y. Agustina, L. N. Istanti, and T. Wijijayanti. "Do Merger and Acquisition Affect on Company's Financial Performance?" *Sriwijaya International Journal of Dynamic Economics and Business*, vol. 1, no. 4, 2017, pp. 375–386.
18. Leepsa, N. M., and C. S. Mishra. "Post Merger Financial Performance: A Study with Reference to Select Manufacturing Companies in India." *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, vol. 83, 2012, pp. 6–17.
19. Li, Y., and X. Geng. "Analyzing the Role of Mergers and Acquisitions and Environmental Investment in Achieving Energy Transition and Sustainability." *Economic Change and Restructuring*, vol. 57, no. 3, 2024, pp. 1–27.
20. Mishra, P., and T. Chandra. "Mergers, Acquisitions and Firms Performance: Experience of Indian Pharmaceutical Industry." *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics*, vol. 3, no. 5, 2010, pp. 111–126.
21. Rani, N., S. S. Yadav, and P. K. Jain. "Financial Performance Analysis of Mergers and Acquisitions: Evidence from India." *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, vol. 25, no. 4, 2015, pp. 402–423.
22. Reddy, K., M. Qamar, and N. Yahanpath. "Do Mergers and Acquisitions Create Value? The Post-M&A Performance of Acquiring Firms in China and India." *Studies in Economics and Finance*, vol. 36, no. 2, 2019, pp. 240–264.
23. Satapathy, D. P., and K. P. Kaushik. "Do Financial Performance Improve after Merger and Acquisition of Acquiring Companies: Evidence from India." *Empirical Economic Letters*, vol. 20, no. 8, 2021, pp. 61–67.
24. Shah, A., E. Phadke, H. Srivastava, and M. Antani. "Navigating the Boom: Rise of M&A in Healthcare." *Nishith Desai Associates*, 23 Aug. 2024, www.nishithdesai.com/ArticleContent/44/14920/Deal-Corner.html. Accessed 18 Sept. 2025.
25. Sharma, J., and I. Singh. "An Empirical Study on Mergers and Acquisitions on Job Security of Employees in Indian Banks." *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia Analitica Junior*, vol. 14, no. 2, 2023, pp. 33–46.
26. Usman, A., U. A. Mehboob, and S. U. Farooq. "Relative Operating Performance of Merged Firms in Pakistan." *European Journal of Economics, Finance & Administrative Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 20, 2010, pp. 44–48.
27. Vinila, T. "Merger of Banks: Indian Perspective." *IJO-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, vol. 6, no. 9, 2023, pp. 1–14.
28. Vinocur, E., H. Kiyamaz, and M. L. Loughry. "M&A Capability and Long-Term Firm Performance: A Strategic Management Perspective." *Journal of Strategy and*

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